

Exponentials and Logarithms: A Rigorous Introduction

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1. Introduction

In secondary school mathematics textbooks, the logarithm is often defined as the inverse of the exponential. In other words, in a pretty much intuitive, but certainly not rigorous fashion, the logarithm of a number in a given base is often defined as the index that one must give to the base to obtain the argument of the logarithm. In spite of the simplicity of this definition, it opens up to a series of subtle problems. For instance, what guarantees that for any base a and argument b , there always is an index x such that, raising the base a to the power x gives the argument b ? In symbols, what guarantees that the equation $a^x = b$ always has one (and only one) solution x ?

But, even more subtly, while it is easy to define the power a^n when n is a positive integer by setting $a^2 = a \cdot a$, $a^3 = a \cdot a \cdot a$, and so on, it is not so easy to express what a^n is, when n is not an integer. The traditional way to do so consists in extending the exponential function is through the algebraic properties of indices. For example, we know that $a^n \cdot a^m = a^{n+m}$. If we wish this identity to hold for every pair of natural numbers n and m , then we must convey that $a^0 = 1$. In fact, this identity yields $a^0 = a^{0+0} = a^0 \cdot a^0$, and the only two numbers that satisfy the equation $x = x^2$ are $x = 0$ and $x = 1$. However, if it was $a^0 = 0$ then we would also necessarily have $a^n = a^{0+n} = a^0 a^n = 0 a^n = 0$ for every n , and since we definitely don't want this to happen, we must conclude that $a^0 = 1$.

In fact, this very property can be exploited even further to extend the exponential function to all integers. To this end, it will suffice to define a^{-n} and this can be easily done by observing that $a^{-n} \cdot a^n = a^{-n+n} = a^0 = 1$. To ensure consistency, then, the number a^{-n} must equate the reciprocal, $1/a^n$, of a^n . It is worth at this point to notice that $a^n = a^{n-m} \cdot a^m$, hence $a^n \div a^m = a^{n-m}$ for every pair of integers n and m .

In order to extend the definition of exponential to every rational index, we will need to utilise a further law of indices. Precisely, let us observe that the property $a^{n+m} = a^n \cdot a^m$ yields $(a^n)^m = a^{nm}$ by simply repeating m times the product of a^n with itself. This latter property shows that $(a^{\frac{1}{n}})^n = a^{\frac{n}{n}} = a^1 = a$, hence $a^{\frac{1}{n}} = \sqrt[n]{a}$. The extension to any rational number $\frac{m}{n}$ is now obvious: it suffices to set $a^{\frac{m}{n}} = \sqrt[n]{a^m}$.

The approach utilised so far, consisting in algebraically extending the exponential function starting from the very intuitive definition for all positive integers seems promising, but unfortunately it terminates here, because the next extension from rational to real numbers cannot be done exploiting the algebraic properties of the indices, but is going to require the finest properties of real numbers, which are complicated and tedious. Trying to follow this route would open up a can of worms that is generally not worth the effort, and secondary school textbooks solve the problem hiding the dust under the carpet and becoming sloppy. Some that pretend to be slightly more rigorous decide to summon the almighty continuity of a function, but none bothers defining what this fundamental term actually means.

The purpose of the present article is to bypass the difficulties linked with the fine properties of real numbers, and give a definition that is perhaps initially not quite as intuitive, but that has the advantage of being rigorous. This can be obtained by taking a slightly different route than the usual: we shall begin by stating the definition of natural logarithm, then walking backwards to give the general definition of exponential function, and we shall see, along the way, how the exponential function is actually one, and all the other are related to this particular one by a simple formula. In the end, we shall find that, when the argument is integer, or rational, our new-born function will coincide with the one intuitively described before, but the new exponential function will have a much stronger theoretical background.

2. The definition of natural logarithm

Let us consider the function L defined for every positive real number x by

$$L(x) = \int_1^x \frac{1}{u} du$$

Observe immediately that, since the real function $1/u$ is not defined at $u = 0$, the function $L(x)$ is only defined for $x > 0$. Furthermore, the function $1/u$ is positive on the interval between 1 and x and therefore the function $L(x)$ is negative for $0 < x < 1$, positive for $x > 1$ and $L(1) = 0$.

(2.1) Proposition. *For every positive pair of real numbers x and y ,*

$$L(xy) = L(x) + L(y).$$

PROOF. By definition,

$$L(xy) = \int_1^{xy} \frac{1}{u} du = \int_1^x \frac{1}{u} du + \int_x^{xy} \frac{1}{u} du.$$

The first of these integrals is $L(x)$. To complete the proof, it suffices to apply the substitution $u = xz$ to the second integral. In fact, if $u = xz$, then $du = x dz$. As regard to the extremes of integration, observe that, when $u = x$, then $z = 1$, and when $u = xy$, then $z = y$, so $\int_x^{xy} (1/u) du = \int_1^y (1/z) dz = L(y)$. \square

The definition of the function L and the previous proposition show that L does have the following two properties:

$$L(1) = 0, \quad L(xy) = L(x) + L(y) \quad \text{for all } x, y > 0.$$

This is sufficient to give the following definition.

(2.2) Definition. The function

$$L(x) = \int_1^x \frac{1}{u} \, du$$

defined for every positive real number x , is called the **(natural) logarithm**, and it is denoted by $\ln(x)$.

Let's now look into the properties of the natural logarithm. First off, observe that, by means of the fundamental theorem of calculus, we have

$$y = \ln(x) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{1}{x}.$$

In particular, this means that, for every positive real number x , one has $dy/dx > 0$, which ensures that the function $y = \ln(x)$ is everywhere increasing.

The next result is perhaps even easier to prove, but it deserves its own proposition, with its number and a neat proof, not quite because it is difficult, but because it is important.

(2.3) Proposition. *If x and y are positive real numbers, then*

$$\ln(xy) = \ln(x) + \ln(y), \quad \ln\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) = \ln(y) - \ln(x).$$

PROOF. Assume that x and y are two positive real numbers. The first of these two formulae is just $L(xy) = L(x) + L(y)$, which was proved in Proposition (2.1); this time it is just written with the 'ln notation'. To prove the second formula, it suffices to observe that, from the (obvious) identity $y = xy/x$, from the first formula, it follows that $L(y) = L(xy/x) = L(x) + L(y/x)$, hence $L(y/x) = L(y) - L(x)$. The second formula then follows by rewriting this one with the 'ln notation'. \square

Besides the two fundamental properties of logarithms stated in Proposition (2.3), there is a third one. We are not yet in condition to state it in full generality, but, for the moment, we can content to prove a special case, which is going to end up being quite useful, anyway. That is why I am going to call the next a 'lemma' rather than a 'proposition'.

(2.4) Lemma. *For every positive real number x and every integer n ,*

$$\ln(x^n) = n \ln(x).$$

PROOF. Let us start by assuming that n is non-negative and let us argue by induction. In fact, if $n = 0$, the left-hand side is $\ln(x^0) = \ln(1) = 0$ and so it is trivially the right-hand side, for $0 \cdot \ln(x) = 0$. Now suppose that there is an integer k such that $\ln(x^k) = k \ln(x)$ and let us prove that $\ln(x^{k+1}) = (k+1) \ln(x)$. Indeed, by means of Proposition (2.3),

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(x^{k+1}) &= \ln(x^k \cdot x) \\ &= \ln(x^k) + \ln(x) \\ &= k \ln(x) + \ln(x) \\ &= (k+1) \ln(x). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the formula holds for $n = 0$, and if the formula holds for $n = k$ it also holds for $n = k + 1$, therefore the formula holds for every non-negative integer n by mathematical induction. To extend the formula to all negative integers, take $\ln(x^{-n})$ where n is a positive integer, and observe that, by definition of negative power, one has $x^{-n} = 1/x^n$, so

$$\ln(x^{-n}) = \ln\left(\frac{1}{x^n}\right) = \ln(1) - \ln(x^n) = -n \ln(x).$$

Thus, the equality $\ln(x^n) = n \ln(x)$ holds for every positive real number x and every integer n . \square

Let's move back to the geometrical properties of the function $y = \ln(x)$ and observe that, when x tends to 0 from the right, the function $\ln(x)$ tends to negative infinite. Indeed, it suffices to see that $\ln(2^{-n}) = -n \ln(2)$ and take the limit as n approaches $+\infty$. Similarly, the function $\ln(x)$ tends to infinite when x tends to $+\infty$. For this, it suffices to take $\ln(2^n) = n \ln(2)$ and take the limit as n approaches $+\infty$. In summary,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} \ln(x) = -\infty, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \ln(x) = +\infty.$$

All the geometrical properties of the curve with equation $y = \ln(x)$ can now be summarised into a graph, like the one in Figure 2.1.

Even though I want really badly to steer clear of the mathematical definition of continuity, which is complicated and confusing, let us just mention that a function $f(x)$ is **continuous** at a point c if it is true that $f(x) \rightarrow f(c)$ as $x \rightarrow c$. All that we want to take from the definition of continuity is that the function $y = \ln(x)$ is continuous at any point c . In fact, if c is a positive real number, and if ε is a positive real number, small enough to have $0 < c - \varepsilon$, suppose that $c - \varepsilon < x < c + \varepsilon$, and observe that

$$|\ln(x) - \ln(c)| = \left| \int_1^x \frac{1}{u} du - \int_1^c \frac{1}{u} du \right| = \left| \int_c^x \frac{1}{u} du \right| \leq \frac{1}{c - \varepsilon} |x - c|$$

as x approaches c , this quantity tends to zero, hence $\ln(x) \rightarrow \ln(c)$.

Figure 2.1. The diagram shows the function $y = \ln(x)$.

To be honest, this in fact happens every time that a function is defined as the integral of another function that is decent enough. Though it is tempting to now open a long discussion on what the phrase ‘decent enough’ means, I will limit myself to claiming that all functions available to a secondary school student are decent enough. In reality, all functions available to most of the average user of differential and integral calculus are ‘decent enough’. To find a function that is not decent, one must really make a conscious effort in that specific direction, so there is absolutely no way that anyone can plug an indecent function into an integral ‘by accident’.

3. The exponential function

The properties of the logarithm function $\ln(x)$ that we have proved in the previous section ensure that the function $\ln(x)$ is strictly increasing and takes every real value. Thus, the function $\ln(x)$ is invertible, i.e. there exists the inverse function. Let us denote it by $\exp(x)$. Then, the function $\exp(x)$ may be defined as the only function on the set of all real numbers x , with value in the set of all positive real numbers, characterised by the relations $\ln(\exp(x)) = x$ for every real number x , and $\exp(\ln(y)) = y$ for every positive real number y . This is a good starting point to define the exponential function.

(3.1) Definition. In the same hypotheses as in Definition (2.2), the only real function $\exp(x)$ such that

$$\ln(\exp(x)) = x, \quad \exp(\ln(y)) = y$$

for every real number x , and every positive real number y is called the **exponential function**.

Let us start by observing that the function $\exp(x)$ takes any real number x and returns a positive real number. Furthermore, the graph of $y = \exp(x)$ can be obtained from the graph of $y = \ln(x)$ by applying the transformation $x' = y$ and $y' = x$, i.e. by a reflection about the straight line with equation $y = x$. The result is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. The diagram shows the exponential function $y = \exp(x)$. Observe that the graph is the reflection about the straight line with equation $y = x$ of the natural logarithm function $y = \ln(x)$.

If we wish to consider the exponential function just defined to be our candidate to extend the expression a^x from every rational number x to every real number, we first need to show that the exponential function $y = \exp(x)$ satisfies properties analogues to the laws of indices. In fact, any candidate to be the extension of a^x not only must coincide with it whenever x is rational, but should also retain the same properties, extending them to all real numbers.

(3.2) Proposition. *In the same hypotheses as in Definition (3.1), $\exp(0) = 1$. Furthermore, for every pair of real numbers x and y , and every integer n , we have*

$$\exp(x + y) = \exp(x) \exp(y), \quad \exp(y - x) = \frac{\exp(y)}{\exp(x)}, \quad \exp(x)^n = \exp(nx).$$

PROOF. The first statement is obvious: from the equality $\ln(1) = 0$ it follows that $\exp(0) = 1$. To prove the first formula, it suffices to observe that, from the equality $\ln(uv) = \ln(u) + \ln(v)$, taking $u = \exp(x)$ and $v = \exp(y)$, we

get $\ln(\exp(x)\exp(y)) = x + y$. Applying again the function \exp on both sides of the latter equality yields $\exp(x)\exp(y) = \exp(x + y)$ as required. The second formula is a simple consequence of the first. To see this, start with observing that

$$\exp(y) = \exp(y - x + x) = \exp(y - x)\exp(x)$$

and the formula is obtained dividing throughout by $\exp(x)$. To prove the third formula, let us start by assuming that n is a non-negative integer, and let us argue by induction. When $n = 0$ there is not much to prove: the left-hand side is obviously $\exp(x)^0 = 1$, and the right-hand side is also $\exp(0) = 1$. Assume therefore that the formula holds when $n = k$ and let us prove it when $n = k + 1$. In other words, let us prove that $\exp(x)^{k+1} = \exp((k + 1)x)$. In fact,

$$\begin{aligned} \exp(x)^{k+1} &= \exp(x)^k \exp(x) \\ &= \exp(kx)\exp(x) \\ &= \exp(kx + x) \\ &= \exp((k + 1)x). \end{aligned}$$

Since the formula (trivially) holds for $n = 0$, and if the formula holds for $n = k$, then it also holds for $n = k + 1$, it holds for every positive integer n by mathematical induction. It remains to prove that the formula also holds when n is negative. To this end observe that it is sufficient to prove that $\exp(x)^{-1} = \exp(-x)$. This is pretty much obvious, though. In fact, since

$$1 = \exp(0) = \exp(x - x) = \exp(x)\exp(-x),$$

the thesis follows dividing throughout by $\exp(x)$. □

As a straightforward consequence of Proposition (3.2), it is easy to show that, inductively, $\exp(n) = \exp(n \cdot 1) = \exp(1)^n$. Thus, setting $e = \exp(1)$, it is now clear that $\exp(n) = e^n$ for every positive integer n .

(3.3) Definition. The number $e = \exp(1)$ is called **Napier's number**.

Notice that since \exp and \ln are the inverse of one another, the definition of the Napier's number as $e = \exp(1)$ entails $\ln(e) = 1$. It is also nice to see this definition in terms of the very definition of \ln as an integral function. Precisely, e is the only number such that

$$\int_1^e \frac{1}{u} du = 1.$$

In more geometrical terms, the area between the curve $y = 1/x$, the x -axis and the vertical lines $x = 1$ and $x = e$, shaded in Figure 3.2, is equal to one.

The following proposition gives a characterisation of the Napier's number, that can be used to give an approximation of this number, although more efficient algorithms may be found e.g. using calculus.

(3.4) Proposition. We have

$$e = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n$$

Figure 3.2. The diagram shows the function $y = 1/x$. By definition of the number e , the shaded area, between the function, the x -axis, and the vertical lines $x = 1$ and $x = e$ is equal to 1.

PROOF. By definition, $e = \exp(1)$ or, equivalently, $\ln(e) = 1$. It suffices therefore to show that the latter identity holds. To this end, observe that, by virtue of the properties of logarithm,

$$\ln\left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n\right) = n \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) = n \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{n}} \frac{1}{u} du.$$

From the mean value theorem, for every positive integer n , there exist a constant c_n with $1 < c_n < 1 + \frac{1}{n}$, such that

$$\int_1^{1+\frac{1}{n}} \frac{1}{u} du = \frac{1}{nc_n}.$$

Hence,

$$\ln\left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n\right) = n \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{n}} \frac{1}{u} du = \frac{1}{c_n}.$$

Taking the limit as n approaches ∞ , the sequence c_n tends towards the constant 1, as it is trapped between 1 and $1 + \frac{1}{n}$, and therefore we get

$$\ln\left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n\right) \rightarrow 1.$$

Since the function $\ln(x)$ is continuous, this means that $\left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n \rightarrow e$ as requested. \square

Let us complete this section by calculating the derivative of the function $\exp(x)$. To this end, consider the function $y = \exp(x)$ and take its inverse function $x = \ln(y)$. Since by definition $\ln(y) = \int_1^y (1/u) du$, from the fundamental theorem of calculus, we know that

$$\frac{dx}{dy} = \frac{1}{y}$$

hence, reciprocating,

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = y.$$

In other words, the derivative dy/dx of the function $y = \exp(x)$ coincides with the function $y = \exp(x)$ itself. In other words, we have just proved the following:

$$y = \exp(x) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{dy}{dx} = \exp(x).$$

4. Exponentials and logarithms in a generic base

Having defined the natural logarithm, $x = \ln(y)$, and the (natural) exponential function, $y = \exp(x)$, and having shown that the exponential has the property that $\exp(n) = e^n$ when n is a positive integer, we can now apply the same argument used at the beginning of Section 1, and infer that $\exp(x) = e^x$ for every rational number x . However, it looks like the initial argument was more promising because it enabled to define the exponential function with any positive base $a \neq 1$, while our exponential function $\exp(x)$ only uses a special base, e , which may look like an obscure number. To extend our definition of exponential to any base, let us start by proving a useful proposition.

(4.1) Proposition. *Suppose that $y = f(x)$ is a differentiable function defined for every positive real number x , such that*

$$f(1) = 0, \quad f(xy) = f(x) + f(y) \quad \text{for every } x, y > 0.$$

Then there exists a real number c such that $f(x) = c \ln(x)$.

PROOF. Assume that $f(x)$ is differentiable, and let us use implicit differentiation to differentiate $f(xy) = f(x) + f(y)$ with respect to x . This gives $yf'(xy) = f'(x)$. Setting $x = 1$ and $c = f'(1)$, this takes the form $f'(y) = c/y$. Integrating both sides of the previous equality finally gives $f(x) = c \int_1^x (1/y) dy = c \ln(x)$. \square

In the same hypotheses as Proposition (4.1), let us now observe that, since the function $\ln(x)$ takes every real value, the constant c may always be written in the form $c = 1/\ln(a)$, for a certain positive real number a . The function $f(x)$ can therefore be written in its final form

$$f(x) = \frac{\ln(x)}{\ln(a)}.$$

This is called the **logarithm in the base a of x** and it is denoted by $\log_a(x)$. It is worth to notice that the main difference between $\ln(x)$ and $\log_a(x)$ is that while $\ln(e) = 1$, one has $\log_a(a) = 1$. On the other hand, all the other algebraic properties of the function $f(x) = \log_a(x)$ remain the same as those of $\ln(x)$, including the fact that this function is always invertible. Its inverse, that can be at least momentarily written as $\exp_a(x)$, has the property that $\exp_a(1) = a$ and

therefore $\exp_a(n) = a^n$. Thus, the function $\exp_a(x)$ can be taken as the definition of the **exponential with base a of x** . Now, since the function $\exp_a(x)$ coincides with a^x when x is a rational number, and since the function $\exp_a(x)$ satisfies to all the index laws, we shall utilise preferably the notation a^x to denote $\exp_a(x)$. In particular, $e^x = \exp(x)$.

Let us also notice that, since $x = \log_a(y) = c \ln(y)$ with $c = 1/\ln(a)$, then $y = e^{x/c} = e^{x \ln(a)}$. This proves that all exponential functions and all logarithm functions are related by the formulae

$$a^x = e^{x \ln(a)}, \quad \log_a(x) = \frac{\ln(x)}{\ln(a)}$$

which are called the **change of base formula** for the exponential and the logarithm, respectively.

Our last effort consists in finding the derivative of the function $y = a^x$. To this end, set $c = 1/\ln(a)$ and take the inverse $x = c \ln(y)$. We have

$$\frac{dx}{dy} = \frac{c}{y}$$

and, reciprocating the previous equality, gives

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{y}{c} = y \ln(a),$$

which shows that the derivative of a^x is directly proportional to the function a^x itself, and that the constant of proportionality is $\ln(a)$. Furthermore, the only function whose derivative is exactly the function itself, i.e. which is proportional to itself with constant of proportionality 1, is the (natural) exponential e^x .

5. Extra properties of logarithms and exponentials

The previous section shows that the rigorous definition of the exponential a^x , where a is a positive real number and x is a real number is

$$a^x = \exp(x \ln(a)).$$

Furthermore, we have seen that, when x is a rational number, this definition coincides with the intuitive definition of exponential, i.e. $a^n = a \cdot a \cdot a \cdots a$, n times. We have also seen that the logarithm function satisfies the following three properties: $\ln(xy) = \ln(x) + \ln(y)$, $\ln(x/y) = \ln(x) - \ln(y)$ and $\ln(x^n) = n \ln(x)$. Now, since $\log_a(x) = c \ln(x)$ when $c = 1/\ln(a)$, these formulae instantly extend to any logarithm, by simply multiplying throughout by c . Furthermore, the latter formula can now be further generalised. Indeed, the following is true.

(5.1) Proposition. *Let x be a positive real number, a a positive real number, with $a \neq 1$, and α be a real number. Then,*

$$\log_a(x^\alpha) = \alpha \log_a(x).$$

PROOF. Let us start by proving the formula for $a = e$. In this special case, by definition of the function $\ln(x)$, we have

$$\ln(x^\alpha) = \int_1^{x^\alpha} \frac{1}{u} du.$$

Let's perform the substitution $u = w^\alpha$. Then $du = \alpha w^{\alpha-1} dw$. For the extremes of integration, when $u = 1$, then $w = 1$, and when $u = x^\alpha$, then $w = x$. Thus,

$$\ln(x^\alpha) = \int_1^{x^\alpha} \frac{1}{u} du = \int_1^x \frac{\alpha w^{\alpha-1}}{w^\alpha} dw = \alpha \int_1^x \frac{1}{w} dw = \alpha \ln(x).$$

To complete the proof, we only need to extend the formula to any base a . To this end, it suffices to divide the identity $\ln(x^\alpha) = \alpha \ln(x)$ by $\ln(a)$, and the result is now fully proved. \square

So, to recap, if a is a positive real number, with $a \neq 1$, x and y are two positive real numbers and α is any real number, the logarithm function, \log_a , enjoys the following properties:

$$\log_a(1) = 0, \quad \log_a(a) = 1$$

$$\log_a(xy) = \log_a(x) + \log_a(y)$$

$$\log_a\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) = \log_a(x) - \log_a(y)$$

$$\log_a(x^\alpha) = \alpha \log_a(x)$$

The equivalent of the result in Proposition (5.1) for exponentials is the following.

(5.2) Proposition. *Let x and y be two real numbers, and a a positive real number with $a \neq 1$. Then*

$$(a^x)^y = a^{xy}$$

PROOF. By virtue of Proposition (5.1), we know that

$$\log_a((a^x)^y) = y \log_a(a^x) = xy.$$

The result follows taking the exponential of both sides of the previous identity. \square

So, to recap, if x , y and α are three real numbers, and a is a positive real number, with $a \neq 1$, the exponential function enjoys the following properties:

$$a^0 = 1, \quad a^1 = a$$

$$a^{x+y} = a^x a^y \quad a^{x-y} = \frac{a^x}{a^y}$$

$$(a^x)^y = a^{xy}$$